

Fox Insight Parkinson’s Disease Microbiome (PDMB) Survey Data

Stagaman Survey Data (2024)

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Summary

This report addresses data quality issues identified in the Fox Insight PD Microbiome (PDMB) metadata and survey data resources hosted on [Fox DEN](#). Multiple researchers have [identified](#) discrepancies that, without clarification, limit the usability of the dataset for research purposes.

The dataset in question is the Stagaman Survey data (2024) [[Stagman_2024_Survey_Data_2024-11-15.tsv](#)] available for download from the [Fox DEN](#) homepage > Recent Publications > Stagaman Survey data (2024).

Problem Statement

During routine analysis of the Fox Insight PD Microbiome (PDMB) dataset, researchers identified multiple data quality issues that affect both case-control classification and demographic

metadata completeness. Without clarification, these discrepancies limit the dataset's utility in its current state.

Identified Issues and Solutions / Explanations

Missing Control Group Metadata

Initial investigations revealed incomplete metadata for control participants, with the primary `Stagman_2024_Survey_Data_2024-11-15.tsv` file appearing to contain only limited participant data rather than comprehensive demographic information for both cases and controls.

i Explanation

These data are not the comprehensive demographic data for the PDMB microbiome dataset, but rather the metadata/survey data that were used in [Stagaman et al. \(2024\)](#). These data are a subset of all PDMB data and represent the highest-quality case and control data that were not excluded for Presequencing QC, participant age filtering, gastroenteritis, and rarefaction to minimum read count > 10,000 (see Supplementary Materials to Stagaman et al., 2024). Participants with missing survey data were either excluded from analyses or withdrew consent (see Additional Findings).

Missing Control Participant Records

Control participant IDs are absent from the Stagaman Survey data (2024), including participants: 17, 23, 31, 50, 55, 67, 80, 92, 93, 96, 105, 111, 151, 154, 162, 183, 188, 189, 190, 212, 220, 229, 233, 235, 250, 257, 258, 261, 270, 277, 280, and 287.

i Explanation

These participants were excluded due to presequencing QC, participant age filtering, gastroenteritis, and rarefaction to minimum read count > 10,000 (see Supplementary Materials to Stagaman et al., 2024) or consent status (see Additional Findings).

Data Integrity Problems in Case Classification

Improper ID Formatting: Multiple PD cases are recorded with simple numerical identifiers (e.g., “001”, “009”, “019”) instead of the standard `FOX_#####` format typically used for Parkinson's disease participants.

i Explanation

FoxDEN_ID identifiers without the “FOX_” prefix indicate participants recruited and collected via 23andMe, Inc.

Duplicate Entries: Numerous participants appear multiple times in the dataset with identical case/control classifications, suggesting data processing errors.

i Explanation

Participants are represented in up to 2 rows in the dataset. One row is designated as “Saliva” and the other will be designated as “Stool” in the column `sample_type`. The survey data is necessarily duplicated across the rows and is intentional, as the survey data is tied to FoxDEN_ID. In other words, data are in long format with respect to `sample_type`.

Misclassification Issues: Cross-referencing revealed participants labeled as “controls” in the microbiome data who are classified as PD cases according to survey responses.

i Explanation

The absence of a “Fox_” prefix for the FoxDEN_ID column does not necessarily indicate control status. We encourage researchers to use the `parkinsons` column in `Stagman_2024_Survey_Data_2024-11-15.tsv` to identify case/control status when working with the PDMB data for replication purposes. For the most recent PD status on Fox Insight participants (Fox_ prefix), we recommend researchers check against `CurrPDDiag` available on Fox DEN, as PD status may change across longitudinal data collections.

Missing Identifiers: Some PD cases appear in the dataset with no participant identifier at all, making them impossible to link with other study data.

i Explanation

There are $n=2$ PD cases without a FoxDEN_ID identifier for both stool and saliva `sample_type` (4 total rows). These participants’ data were unable to be decoded across files that link FoxDEN_IDs to microbiome sample IDs.

Table 1. Differences in sample sizes between available PDMB metadata and Stagaman et al. (2024).

Source	PD Case		Control	
	Saliva	Stool	Saliva	Stool
Stagaman et al. (2024)	438	445	220	221
Stagman_2024_Survey_Data_2024-11-15.tsv	432	435	214	214
Missing n	6	10	6	7
Withdrew Consent	4	8	6	7
Crosswalk error (missing ID, PD status available)	2	2	0	0
Outstanding rows	0	0	0	0

Rows of missing data: there are 2 rows with complete missing data.

i Explanation

The two rows of entirely missing data can be discarded. These missing rows are an artifact of joining multiple datasets where a participant’s ID was unable to be decoded and who also happened to be excluded from the study.

Additional Findings

When comparing against the reported samples sizes in [Stagaman et al. \(2024\)](#), the `Stagman_2024_Survey_Data_2024-11-15.tsv` file contains fewer samples than published. These reduced numbers can be explained by two factors: consent status and crosswalk decoding. When these data were prepared for sharing on [Fox DEN](#), consent status was checked and participants that withdrew consent were excluded (see Table 1). Survey data from an additional $n=2$ participants were unable to be linked to their respective `FoxDEN_IDs`.

Recommendations

We recommend researchers utilize the `parkinsons` column to establish case/control status of the PDMB participants, which reflects the participants’ PD status nearest to the time of sample collection. If a more recent/updated PD status for Fox Insight participants (`Fox_` prefix) is desired, we recommend researchers check against `CurrPDDiag` available on Fox DEN, as PD status may change across longitudinal data collections.

Rows with entirely missing data can be discarded. The remaining rows with complete data for `FoxDEN_ID` and `parkinsons` status will enable the analysis of participants with high-quality microbiome sequencing data according to exclusionary criteria outlined in [Stagaman et al. \(2024\)](#).